

Cost Efficiency of Maize Production in Ovia North East Area of Edo State, Nigeria

Author Details:

Igbinidu Osayande; Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension Services, University of Benin, Edo State

Abstract

This study examined empirically cost efficiency production in Ovia North East Local Government Area of Edo State using farm-level data with a view to analyse the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, estimate the efficiency of resource allocation of yam farmers in the study area. A two-stage sampling technique was used to collect data from 100 maize farmers with the use of a well-structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution and percentages were used to analysed objective 1) while Cobb-Douglas Stochastic Frontier Cost Function as used to analyse objectives 2). The study revealed that majority (76%) of the maize farmers were within the age brackets of 31 – 60 years and were males whose primary occupation was farming, (67%) and most of them are small-scale farmers. The average cost efficiency estimates were found to be 1.09 implying that the farmers were cost inefficient as they were spending 9% above the minimum cost of production. All the cost items included in the cost function affected the cost efficiency positively and were significant at 5% level of probability except the quantity of maize which was not significant at any rate, sex, level of education and household size were captured as factors determining cost efficiency in the study area. The cost efficiency can be improved by providing input subsidies and enhancing production technology to enable them to enjoy the benefits of economies of scale.

Keywords; Cost Efficiency, Maize production, smallholder farms

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Maize, rice, and wheat are the three leading food crops; unlike wheat and rice, most maize is consumed indirectly as feed for livestock rather than directly as human food. In parts of Latin America, and Sub-Saharan Africa however, most maize is grown for human consumption, and the diet consists largely of maize (Major Goodman, 1979). The chief maize producing regions include the United States of America (especially the Corn Belt region of the North Central states) which produces almost half of the world's total, southeastern Europe (especially, the USSR, Romania Yugoslavia, Hungary, and Italy) China, Brazil, Mexico, South Africa, Argentina, India and Indonesia. Only about 5 percent of USA crop is exported, and that is over half of world production level while western Europe and Japan are the major importers (Simmonds, 1979).

In Africa, South Africa is a major exporter. In recent times there has been a paradigm shift in production with Africa accounting for 6.5% of the world maize output (FAO, 2007). Maize is a staple food crop for the most part of Sub-Saharan African countries of which Nigeria is inclusive with per capita kg/year of 40 million metric tonnes (FAO STAT, 2003). In Nigeria, maize is the third most important cereal crop after sorghum and Millet (Ojo, 2000), the demand for maize as a result of various domestic uses shows that the domestic demand of 3.5 million metric tonnes outstrips supply with production base around 2 million metric tonnes which presents a problem of supply deficit, this deficit can be traced to great demand for maize supply due mainly to transforming them to various end products along the entire value chain.

Although, maize is the most important staple food of great socio-economic importance in Nigeria. At any rate, the decline in maize production in recent years may not be unconnected to farm level inefficiency and other exogenous variables beyond the control of the smallholder farmers – such as price fluctuation, disease, and pest. In exploring the former factors, an improvement in the understanding of the levels of resource use-efficiency, production costs and its relationship with a host of other farm-level factors can greatly aid policymakers in creating policy options that can generate reforms as well as in judging the efficiency of present and past reforms (Maurice, 2004). The broad study objective was to analyse the cost efficiency of maize production in Ovia North-East Local Government Area of Edo-state, with a specific objective, too:

- 1) Examine the socio-economic characteristics of maize farmers in the study area, and
- 2) Determine the efficiency of resource allocation in maize production in the study area.

2.0: Methodology

2.1 Study Area

Edo State was created on August 27, 1991, by the administration of President Ibrahim Badamosi Babangida. The state was excised from the former Bendel State due to popular demand for the state. Edo State is an inland state in western Nigeria; its Capital is Benin city. It has a population of 3,233,366 people (National Population Census, 2006) having a geographical orientation of 5° 44'N and 7°34'N latitudes and 5° 4'E¹ and 6° 45'E¹ longitudes with a total land area of 17,802km² (6,875 50pm). It is bounded in the North and East by Kogi State, in the South by Delta State and in the West by Ondo State, Edo state is inhabited mainly by the following ethnic groups: the Benin, the Esan, the Etsako, the Ora, the Igbanke and the Owan tribes.

Edo state has a tropical climate characterized by two distinct seasons, the wet and dry seasons. The wet season usually lasts from April to November and the dry season from December to March. The state is characterized by adequate rainfall ranging from 800 – 1600mm annually with adverse vegetation ranging from Sudan Savannah to mangrove swamp and large floodplains of fadama sites (Ministry of Agriculture and National Resources, 2009). The major occupation of the people is predominantly farming, although many are also engaged in other occupation.

2.2: Sampling Technique

The population of the study comprises all the maize-farmers in Ovia North East Local Government Area of Edo State. Since it is impracticable and uneconomical to survey all farmers the following two-stage procedure was used to arrive at our sample size;

First stage: This involved a purposive selection of four (4) maize villages in Ovia North-East Local Government Area which include Ovbiogie, Isihor, Okokhuo, and Urhonigbe, based on researcher's *apriori* knowledge of the area as having maize production intensity and markets.

The second and final stage involved a random sampling selection of one hundred (100) farmers from a list of maize farmers in the study area. This is aimed at ensuring fair and equal coverage of each of the council wards.

2.3: Analytic Techniques

Descriptive statistics such as frequency count, percentages and mean, will be used to describe the sample value of selected socio-economic variables whilst Cobb-Douglas stochastic frontier cost function is employed to model maize production technology in this study, because of the following reasons; (i) the functional form has been used in many empirical studies, particularly, those relating to developing country agriculture (Ajibefun *et al*, 2002 and Bravo-Ureta *et al* 1997) (ii) the functional form also meets the requirement of being self-dual that is allowing an examination of economic efficiency.

The estimating equation for the stochastic function is given as:

$$\ln Q = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln x_1 + \beta_2 \ln x_2 + \beta_3 \ln x_3 + \dots - \beta_5 \ln x_5 + v - u_2$$

The maximum likelihood estimated of above equation provides estimators for b's variance parameters ($\sigma^2 = \sigma_u^2 + \sigma_v^2$), gamma (g), which is equal to σ_v^2 / σ^2 and lambda (1) = σ^2 / ay . The parameter gamma (g) has a value between zero and one (Baltesse and Tessema, 1993). The gamma (g) measures the technical inefficiency, similarly (1-g) measures the technical inefficiency of the farm firm. The parameter lambda (1) is expected to be greater than one such result indicates good fit for the a a a model and correctness of distributional assumption v and u

The model is specified below as:

$$C_1 = a_0 + a_1 pr_{ii} + a_2 p_{2i} + a_3 p_{3i} + a_4 p_{4i} + a_5 p_{5i} + v + u$$

Although this is the linearized form,

C_1 = total production cost per year

P_1 = the average wage rate per Mandays of labour

P_2 = the price per kg of planting materials (seed)

P_3 = price per kg of fertilizer

P_4 = price of farm tools (Depreciation)

Y_1 = as earlier defined above

The β_s are parameters to be estimated. The frontier functions (production and cost) are estimated through maximum likelihood method. For this study, the computer programme FRONTIER version 4.1c was used. It should be noted that this computer programme estimates the cost efficiency (CE) this has an inverse relationship to farm level economic efficiency.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 The Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 3. shows that the youngest maize farmer was 27 years old. The mean age was 51.95 years old. The bulk of the maize farmers were within the age bracket of 31 – 60 years old which indicates that they are the most economically active and they account for majority (76%) of the maize farmers. Farmers within the age bracket of less than 30 years were the fewest accounting for only 1% of the maize farmers.

The oldest farmer was 83 years old.

Table 1 also revealed that the majority (78%) of the farmers were male while the minority (22%) were females. This highlights the facts that agriculture in this part of the world is still male-dominated this might not be unconnected to a tenurial land system which limits female access to land. This is derived from the social, cultural and economic Limitation which a patrimonial society like ours imposes on females.

On the basis of marital status, Table 3.1 reflected that majority of the farmers (84%) were married while a handful, (2%) of respondents were single as at the time of data collection. It was revealed further down Table 3.1 that 32% of the respondent has no formal education, 30% of the respondents had primary education, 33% of the respondents had a secondary education while 5% of the respondents had tertiary education. Although majority were literate, the 63% of respondents low level of education (primary and secondary) still pose a problem, this grows out of the concern from the findings of Quinzumberg and Meinzen (2011) who opined that many poor countries notably Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) have low level of education and that improving their education will probably increase agricultural productivity and attack poverty. Farm holding of less than 5ha representing 80% predominates in the study area. The small size farm holding could be attributed to farmers' small capital base and poor access to farm inputs. Finally, farmers farming experience of more than 11 years have percentages of 65%. More years of experience implies that farmers have gathered adequate skills and expertise likely to make farming successful.

Table 3.1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
<=30 years	1	1.0
31 – 45 years	38	38.0
46 – 60 years	38	38.0
61 – 75 years	17	17.0
76+ years	6	6.0
Sex		
Male	78	78.0
Female	22	22.0

Marital Status		
Single	2	2.0
Married	84	84.0
Widowed	13	13.0
Divorced	1	1.0
Level of Education		
No formal	32	32.0
Primary	33	33.0
Secondary	5	5.0
Tertiary		
Farm size		
<=0.50ha	6	6.0
0.51 – 1.30ha	53	53.0
1.31 – 2.10ha	37	37.0
2.11 – 2.90ha	2	2.0
2.91 – 3.70ha	1	1.0
3.70+ha	1	1.0
Household size		
<=5	18	18.0
6 – 15	81	81.0
26+	1	1.0
Farming Experience		
<=10 years	35	35.0
11 – 20 years	35	35.0
21 – 30	19	19.0

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

3.2 Descriptive Statistics of Allocative Efficiency Estimates for the Stochastic Frontier Cost Function, Empirical Results of the parameters of the stochastic frontier cost function

The results of the estimate of the parameters in the Cobb-Douglas stochastic cost function is presented in Table 3.2, the significance of sigma square (0.03) at 5% level indicates a good fit and the correctness of the specified distributional assumption of the model. This implies that Cobb-Douglas stochastic function fits the data better.

Furthermore, the estimated value of gamma (0.99) which is the ratio of the variance of farm-specific cost inefficiency was high and significant at 5% level. This implies that about 99% of the variation from the minimum cost among maize farmers was due to the inefficiency on the part of the farmers instead of random variability.

Table 2: Maximum Likelihood (ML) Estimate of the Parameters of cost Functions

Variables	Coefficient	Standard-error	t-ratio
Constant	1.0491	0.085	12.6302**
Quantity of maize	-0.0027	0.0051	-0.5380
Fertilizer cost	0.1859	0.0117	15.9331**
Labour cost	0.6061	0.0135	44.9670**
Seed cost	0.0799	0.0080	9.9976**
Depreciation	0.1329	0.0102	13.0750**
Inefficiency Model			
Constant	-0.0185	0.1778	-0.1042
Age	0.0026	0.0030	0.8719
Sex	-0.6052	0.1060	-5.7088**
Level of Education	0.1131	0.3262	3.4683**
Years of Experience	0.0030	0.0034	0.8789
Household Size	-0.0491	0.0056	-8.8015**
Sigma-squared	0.0383	0.0043	8.9309
Gamma	0.9997	0.0007	1439.8838
LR			
	0.10549773E+03		

Source: Field Survey, 2015

**significant at 5%

3.3 Allocative Inefficiency Model

The sign of the coefficient of the variable in the inefficiency model is very crucial in explaining the observed level of efficiency of the farmers. The results in Table 3.2, shows that sex (-5.7088) and household size (-8.8015) at 5% level of significance were negative significant which implied that household size and sex produces a negative effect on the allocative inefficiency, which in turn infer that the above duo socio-economic variable reduce cost efficiency while leveling of education increase the cost efficiency in maize production.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusion has been drawn. Male farmers dominated the study area and are mostly between the ages of 31 and 60 years and are fairly educational advantaged since most of them had both primary and secondary education and most are small scale farmers. The average cost (allocative) efficiency of 1.06 indicated that farmers spent 6% above the cost frontier which further implies that maize farmers do not cost effective in the study. To mitigate the future problem, the following recommendation was suggested;

- (1) The costs of input and equipment used for production mostly fertilizers, seeds and pesticides should be subsidized in order for farmers to get easy access to them.
- (2) Farmers should be encouraged to form farmers' co-operative societies to enable them to pool resources together for adequate procurements of resources or inputs
- (3) Better transportation channels should be provided between the study area and urban areas in order for the farm products to be transported to various markets

3.4 Cost of Efficiency Range

The results in Table 3.3 reveals that majority of the respondent (89%) operated within the cost effective range of 1.01 – 1.50, the results further indicated that the estimated cost efficiency varied widely among the maize farmers in the study area, ranging from a minimum of 1.0013 to a maximum of 2.073, on the average, a farmer was found to operate at cost efficiency estimated at 1.066. this implies the farmer is spending 6% above the minimum cost.

Table 3.3: Cost Efficiency Range

Range	Frequency	Percentage
1.00 & below	10	10.0
1.01 – 1.50	89	89.0
1.51 & above	1	1.0

Source: Field Survey, 2015

Mean efficiency = 1.066

Minimum efficiency = 1.0013

Maximum efficiency = 2.073

References

- i. Major Goodman, M. (1979). *Maize, North Carolina State University, Raleigh NC USA. Journal Series of the North Carolina Agricultural Experimental Station, Paper No. 4439, Pp. 37 – 39.*
- ii. Battese, G.E. and Tessema, F.A. (1993). "Estimation of Stochastic Frontier Production Functions with Time-Varying parameters and Technical Efficiencies using panel data from India village" *agricultural Economics vol. 9:313 – 333.*
- iii. Simmond, N. (1979). *Maize, Longman Group Inc., Limited USA.*
- iv. Food and Agriculture Organisation, (2009) *Statistical Division, Maize, Rice and Wheat Area harvested, production quantity and yield.*

- v. *Ojo, S.O. (2000). Factor Productivity in Maize Production in Ondo State, Nigeria, Applied Tropical Agriculture vol.15 Pp 57 – 65.*
- vi. *Maurice, D.C. (2004). Resource Productivity in Cereal Crops production among Fadama Farmers in Adamawa State. M.Sc. Thesis, Unpublished. University of Maiduguri, Nigeria.*
- vii. *National Population Commission, (2006). Nigeria Population Census Figure. Abuja, national Population Commission.*
- viii. *Ajibefun, I.A., Battese, G.E. and Kada, R. (2002). Technical Efficiency. Technological change and productivity of Hired and Family labour in the Japanese Rice Industry” Empirical Economic Letters, 1(1), 21 – 31.*
- ix. *Bravo-Ureta, Boris, E. and Antonio Pinheiro, E. (1997). Technical Economic and Allocative Efficiency in peasant farming: Evidence from the Dominican Republic. The Development Economics 35 – 12 pp 48 – 67 (1997).*
- x. *Quinsumbing, A.R. and Meinzen Dick, R. (2011). Gender in Agriculture; closing the knowledge gap, xvi, 444.*